

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 4.1 Disseminate reports and recommendations to Member States

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

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1 INTRODUCTION

D4.1 Disseminate reports and recommendations to Member States (Month 14).

The deliverable contains the relevant information regarding engagement with Member States on carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilisation (CCU).

1.1 The Zero Emissions Platform Government Group

The Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) hosts a Government Group which was set up as a place for collaboration between European Government stakeholders and the European Commission (DGs ENER, CLIMA, and RTD).

The group has increased strongly over the last years and now includes representatives from 23 Member State Governments active or interested in CCS and CCU, meeting quarterly to mutually exchange on national CCS/CCU developments, as well as representatives from the European Commission.

The group has the following core objectives:

- Support national governments by collecting and disseminating information.
- Ensure an effective liaison between the European Commission and national governments.
- Ensure an effective liaison between industry and national governments.

With several countries preparing national strategies for CCS and CCU and an increasing number of ongoing and planned projects across Europe, the ZEP Government Group is also crucial in the coordination between EU and national strategies, policies, and funding opportunities.

The Government Group also actively fed into the preparation of ZEP's work programme for 2022-2023, making sure that the priorities for the Platform reflected Member States own priorities.

2 GOVERNMENT GROUP MEETINGS DURING THE GRANT PERIOD

Since the start of the grant period in July 2022, the Government Group met four times:

- 4 October 2022
- 6 December 2022
- 7 March 2023
- 28 June 2023.

Meeting agendas are found in the annex.

The following topics were discussed during the meetings:

- Cross-border transport and storage of CO₂ – the implications of the London Protocol and the European Commission analysis paper on the London protocol¹.
- The work of the CCUS Forum Working Groups (WG) on CO₂ infrastructure and Industrial Partnership for CCUS.
- How to include CCUS/CO₂ infrastructure in the revised national energy and climate plans (NECPs) and how ZEP could support in this process.
- Focused presentations about Member State's experiences in developing CCS/CCU and their national policy and funding frameworks.
- Developments from the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Article 6.4 mechanism.
- The set-up of ZEP's Network Projects, specifically its relation to the Government Group and national authorities.
- EU policy files of interest to CCS and CCU – e.g., the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act proposal, the proposal for a Carbon Removals Certification Framework, the Industrial Carbon Management Plan – where feedback from the Government Group was sought.

¹ European Commission (2022). The EU legal framework for crossborder CO₂ transport and storage in the context of the requirements of the London Protocol. Commission services analysis paper for the Information Exchange Group (IEG) under Directive 2009/31/EC – 30.09.2022. Available for consultation [here](#).

3 DISSEMINATION OF MATERIALS

Member States are key stakeholders to the project and are actively consulted in the preparation of materials (e.g., papers, reports). Since the start of the grant period, the following materials were shared with the Member States:

- [ZEP first response paper on the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act](#)
- [ZEP paper on the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act](#)
- [ZEP-led open letter on Article 18 of the Net-Zero Industry Act ‘Strong support for an implementable and pragmatic Net Zero Industry Act Article 18 – solutions to make CCS work’](#)
- [Joint CCSA and ZEP response to the Article 6.4 Supervisory Body call for input on carbon removals](#)
- [ZEP response to the call for input on issues included in the annotated agenda and related annexes of the fifth meeting of the Article 6.4 Supervisory Body](#)
- [ZEP response to the structured public consultation: removal activities under the Article 6.4 mechanism](#)
- [CCUS Forum Conclusions and issue paper of the WG on CO2 infrastructure](#)
- [ZEP report “CCS in a biodiversity and land-use perspective”](#)
- [Joint CCSA and ZEP response to the ICVCM consultation: Core Carbon Principles \(CCPs\), Assessment Framework and Assessment Procedure](#)
- [ZEP response to the call for evidence ‘Development of trans-European transport \(TEN-T\) network in light of war in Ukraine – amended proposal for guidelines’](#)
- [ZEP response to the call for feedback ‘Energy – updating EU legislation to make the EU independent from Russian fossil fuels \(REPowerEU\)’](#)
- [ZEP note ‘Interference in the EU ETS risks delaying efforts to decarbonise’](#)
- [ZEP response to DNV’s call for inputs on the CO2 Storage Directive Guidance Documents](#)
- [ZEP response to DG CLIMA’s consultation on the key features of the Innovation Fund](#)
- [ZEP response to the European Commission consultation on the list of PCI/PMI candidates in CO2 networks](#)
- [ZEP response to the European Commission consultation on competitive bidding schemes for hydrogen under the Innovation Fund](#)
- [ZEP response to DG RTD’s consultation on the Horizon R&I programmes](#)
- [ZEP response to the European Commission call for views on the proposed certification framework for carbon removals](#)
- [ZEP response to the call for feedback on the EU 2040 climate target.](#)

ANNEX 1, GOVERNMENT GROUP MEETING AGENDAS

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 4 October 2022, 10.30 – 15.00 CET

Hybrid meeting (Norway House, 17 rue Archimède Brussels)

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	Chair / ZEP Secretariat	10:30 - 10:35
2 Update on ZEP activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recent ZEP activities 	ZEP Secretariat	10:35 - 10:45
3 Denmark's national programme for CCUS Presentation of the national CCUS strategy	Jasmin Sharzad, Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities	10:45 - 11:25
4 Updates on national CCS/CCU developments Roundtable – Government Group Members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are you involved in cross-border discussions? Are there bottlenecks and/or enablers you can identify? Are there new CCUS funding opportunities? 	All	11:25 - 12:10
5 Guidance on the draft work programme <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP outline work programme 2022-2023 – <i>pre-read 2</i> Are there missing elements in the programme? What would you like to see as focus areas for the next Government Group meetings? 	All	12:10 - 12:40
LUNCH BREAK		12:40 - 13:40
6 How to include more CCUS/CO2 infrastructure in the revised national energy and climate plans? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Will your NECP change regarding CCS and CCU? Will CCS-CCU be included in your strategy? 	All	13:40 - 14:10

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can ZEP support the EC and European governments for increased CCUS inclusion? 		
7	CCUS Forum	All, ZEP Secretariat	14:10 - 14:40
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short updates from the working groups on Vision, CO2 infrastructure and Industrial partnership 		
8	Next meetings	ZEP Secretariat	14:40 - 14:55
	Suggested dates for the next meetings:		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6 December 2022 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 8 March 2023 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 8 June 2023 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 20 September 2023 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 15 November 2023 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 		
9	Final remarks and AOB	Chair	14:55 - 15:00

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 6 December 2022, 10.30 – 12.30 CET

Virtual meeting

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	Chair / ZEP Secretariat	10:30 - 10:35
2 Update on ZEP activities and EU timeline <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recent ZEP activities EU policy and funding timeline 	ZEP Secretariat	10:35 - 10:50
3 Updates on national CCS/CCU developments Roundtable – Government Group Members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update on licensing rounds Update on national CCUS policy, strategy, and funding opportunities 	All	10:50 - 12:00

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC guidance for the review of the NECPs in 2023 • CO2 imports / exports – bilateral agreements and way forward after EC analysis paper 		
4	Guidance on the draft work programme <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZEP work programme 2023 What would you like to see as focus areas of the Government Group?	ZEP Secretariat, All	12:00 - 12:20
5	Next meetings Suggested dates for the next meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 March 2023 (10:30-15:00 – Hybrid) • 8 June 2023 (10:30-15:00 – Hybrid) • 20 September 2023 (10:30-15:00 – Hybrid) • 15 November 2023 (10:30-15:00 – Hybrid) 	ZEP Secretariat	12:20 - 12:25
6	Final remarks and AOB	Chair	12:25 - 12:30

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 7 March 2023, 10.30 – 14.15 CET

Hybrid meeting: Scotland House (Rond-point Robert Schuman 44, 1040 Brussels) and Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> • New chair 	Chair	10:30 - 10:40
2 Updates on national CCS/CCU developments Roundtable – Government Group Members updates	All	10:40 - 11:20
3 The CCS4CEE project	Michał Wendolowski (Bellona Europa)	11:20 - 11:50
4 ZEP's response to the Article 6.4 Supervisory Body call for feedback	Secretariat, All	11:50 - 12:10

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What should ZEP highlight? 		
LUNCH BREAK			
5	ZEP developments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZEP's new Chair • Work Programme • New Network Projects 	ZEP Secretariat	13:00 - 13:20
6	CCS and CCU outlook <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication on a Strategy for CCS and CCU • Green Deal Industrial Plan • How should ZEP engage? What should ZEP highlight? 	ZEP Secretariat, All	13:20 - 13:40
7	Status of CCS in Iceland <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy landscape • Funding and commercial/business models 	Helga Barðadóttir (Ministry of the Environment, Energy and Climate)	13:40 - 14:10
8	Next meeting dates and AOB <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 June 2023 (10:30-15:00, Copenhagen) • 20 September 2023 (10:30-15:00) • 15 November 2023 (10:30-15:00, Berlin) 	Chair, ZEP Secretariat	14:10 - 14:15

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 28 June 2023, 10.30 – 12.30 CEST

Hybrid meeting: Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities (Holmens Kanal 20 DK-1060 Copenhagen, Denmark) and Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	Jasmin Sharzad (Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities)	10:30 - 10:40
2 New ZEP Network Projects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up 	ZEP Secretariat, All	10:40 – 10:55

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possible coordination with Government Group 		
3	Updates on national CCS/CCU developments Roundtable – Government Group member updates <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National developments: policy and funding Bilateral agreements National Energy and Climate Plans, ahead of the EU Strategy for CCS and CCU 	All	10:55 – 11:40
4	The Net-Zero Industry Act proposal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP position – <i>pre-read 2</i> Other points to consider? 	ZEP Secretariat, All	11:40 – 11:55
5	Paris Agreement: carbon removals Article 6.4 mechanism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP responses – <i>pre-reads 3, 4 and 5</i> Future actions? 	ZEP Secretariat, All	11:55 – 12:10
6	CCS updates from the Bonn Climate Change Conference	Stig Sverningsen (Norwegian Ministry of Petroleum and Energy)	12:10 – 12:25
7	Next meeting dates and AOB 20 September 2023 (10:30-15:00) – to be rescheduled 14 November 2023 (10:30-15:00, Berlin)	ZEP Secretariat	12:25 – 12:30